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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 3.7 – INTERACTION SCENARIOS (FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

Deliverable D3.2, Interaction scenarios, defines and describes the methodical components and stages of the transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design process applied in THEIA^{XR} and presents the final results. Chapter 3 also reports on the overlap of scenario-based co-design activities with value-sensitive design and haptic control and interaction design efforts outside of task T3.2, scenario-based co-design of interaction concepts. Transdisciplinary co-design in THEIA^{XR} is defined as the collaboration of academic and non-academic actors at eye-level in the creative process of XR feature ideation, exploration and elaboration. The scenario-based design methodology facilitates co-design by using descriptive stories for outlining the current use of off-highway machines and ideal future scenarios of XR technology for off-highway vehicle operators. In the final version of this deliverable, we present the initial function ideation results and validated interaction scenarios for all use cases.

Table of Contents

Document Identification	2
Executive summary	4
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Transdisciplinary co-design in THEIA ^{XR}	8
2.1 Definition of methodologies	8
2.2 Application of transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design	9
3 Contributions throughout the project.....	12
3.1 Value-sensitive co-design	12
3.2 Haptic control and feedback function ideation and design	13
4 Final integrated interaction scenarios.....	16
4.1 UC1: Snow-grooming	16
4.2 UC2: Logistics	25
4.3 UC3: Construction.....	33
5 Conclusions.....	40
References.....	41

List of Figures

Figure 1: Visualisation of transdisciplinary inputs and results of the co-design process	10
Figure 2: Haptics demos during the workshops in Sterzing (February 2024)	14
Figure 3: Screenshot of UC1 ideation workshop results	16
Figure 4: Snow groomer leaving the garage	18
Figure 5: Light feedback indicates that vehicle is operational.....	18
Figure 6: Weather forecast showing fog on the slope	19
Figure 7: Map screen showing restricted areas	20
Figure 8: Light feedback and projection warning of blade being set too low	21
Figure 9: Projections of lane borders (blue), restricted (red) and completed areas (green)	21
Figure 10: Winch-operation-based restricted area on the map screen (red).....	22
Figure 11: Critical warning of imminent collision	23
Figure 12: Skier highlighted on map screen.....	23
Figure 13: Screenshot of UC2 ideation workshop results	25
Figure 14: Ideal distribution of information on RC desk setup (workshop result)	27
Figure 15: Vehicle as seen through an outside camera on the port (image: VTT)	28
Figure 16: Cabin view of the vehicle (image: VTT)	29
Figure 17: Spreader placement guidance (image: VTT)	30
Figure 18: Spreader placement guidance (image: VTT)	30
Figure 19: Navigation to target truck (image: VTT).....	30
Figure 20: Persons (e. g., truck driver) detected next to truck (image: VTT).....	31
Figure 21: Top-down view of spreader (image: VTT)	32
Figure 22: Visualization for safe reach based on container weight (image: VTT).....	32
Figure 23: Screenshot of UC3 ideation workshop results	33

Figure 24: Excavators on construction site	35
Figure 25: Top bar of the main screen showing essential vehicle data and functions	35
Figure 26: Main screen showing warnings and reports	36
Figure 27: Excavation pit borders projected on ground	36
Figure 28: Main screen showing top-down view and a person behind the vehicle	37
Figure 29: Selection of secondary screen (split screen)	37
Figure 30: Split screen with side-view showing an electrical line proximity warning	38
Figure 31: Light feedback flashing red, warning of a close object on the right vehicle side	38
Figure 32: Report screen with option to add an own report	39

List of Tables

Table 1: Stages of the transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design approach in THEIA ^{XR}	9
Table 2: General questionnaire regarding opportunities for using haptics in the different use cases	14
Table 3: General conclusions from the discussions around the haptics questionnaires in UC1	15
Table 4: Validated UC1 interaction scenario	18
Table 5: Validated UC2 interaction scenario	27
Table 6: Validated UC3 interaction scenario	35

1 Introduction

Introducing new technologies or systems to a workplace is never an easy task. While technical innovation may spark fascination and excitement in some, it will trigger doubts, fear and rejection in others. The same of course had to be expected when we set out to introduce extended reality (XR) technologies to the cabin of off-highway vehicles in THEIA^{XR}. Specifically in the domains of snow grooming, container logistics and construction, we have so far observed both enthusiasm and aversion towards new cabin technologies from operators. In our numerous visits to operator workplaces, we have heard about snow groomer operators getting motion sickness in their vehicles while working in fog, and thus, vehemently rejecting the idea of using an XR headset in the machine on top of that. We have seen a reach stacker operator point out how an info screen to the right side of his cabin precisely obstructs the view into one of the essential side mirrors. We have watched an excavator manufacturer representative and trainer struggling to find a specific setting in the menu of their own manufacturer's software. When listening to the stories and remarks of off-highway vehicle operators, it almost appears like there has been a tradition of introducing well-meant but oftentimes lacking, obstructive or annoying technical features to the cabin. Of course, this perception may be influenced by negativity bias, as many of these features contribute to making work easier and safer. But in the end, new technologies for the cabin, no matter how good their intentions or how great their potential, must suit the needs, expectations and the real working conditions of the operators.

Acquiring a deep understanding of operator (user) needs before any further design and development steps are taken is one of the core principles of human-centred design (HCD). HCD has a long history of successfully being employed mainly in software development and has also seen use in hazardous industrial work domains in recent years [1], [2]. While HCD aims to learn about the requirements of a new system by working with its (intended) users, the prioritisation of requirements and the subsequent design and selection of solutions commonly remains reserved for the design and engineering teams, as a meta-analysis of 265 case studies indicates [3]. This is one of the major issues currently shifting in design, with new concepts such as 21st century design [4] and humanity-centred design [5] emerging in recent years, which call for designing *with* the people instead of just *for* the people, a collaboration between communities and experts. Methodologies like living labs [6] and co-design [7] are already being employed in some domains to involve users more directly in the creative process, mainly in public service design. However, we could not find any evidence of these approaches being employed in industrial research and innovation projects. This is where the transdisciplinary co-design approach used in THEIA^{XR} aims to break new ground.

In THEIA^{XR}, transdisciplinary co-design is being applied to the use cases of snow grooming (UC1), logistics (UC2) and construction (UC3). The delivery date of this final deliverable was postponed from June 2025 to July 2025 to allow for the finalization of validation studies.

In this deliverable, the theoretical and methodical frameworks of co-design and transdisciplinary design will be outlined, followed by a report on how these methodologies have been applied in the WP3 design process (Chapter 2) and beyond (Chapter 3) in THEIA^{XR}. Chapter 4 will provide an overview of the final results of the co-design process.

2 Transdisciplinary co-design in THEIA^{XR}

2.1 Definition of methodologies

Co-design and the broader concept of co-creation have emerged from the field of participatory design, which originated in Northern European countries in the 1970s [7]. While co-creation is a term for any collective creativity, co-design can be considered the application of co-creation in a design process [7], meaning generally that designers (considered experts for the domain of design) collaborate with non-designers (considered experts for their respective domains) as partners. This also implicates a shift in the role of the designer, who is not expected to be in charge of defining the problem and taking the lead in developing solutions anymore, a perception that would pose the risk of creating a power imbalance in the relationship between designers and community [8] and undermine the core principle of co-design. Instead, the responsibility of the designer shifts towards organising and managing the design process [4], enabling non-designers to engage in creative collaboration [7].

Actively involving non-designers in a design process or, more broadly speaking, involving non-academic actors in an academic research process already implies transdisciplinarity. Transdisciplinarity itself has many definitions with various characteristics, which can roughly be sorted into two main schools of thought: Focusing on a unity of knowledge or on social engagement [9]. The “unity of knowledge” school of transdisciplinarity, also called “theoretical” or “Mode 1” transdisciplinarity [10], is concerned with what is beyond and between the disciplines, based on multiple levels of reality and knowledge outside of objective scientific boundaries [11]. The “social engagement” school of transdisciplinarity, also called “practical” or “Mode 2” transdisciplinarity [10], aims “to contribute to both societal and scientific progress” [12], mandating the participation of non-academic actors. In turn, facilitating a high level of engagement of non-academic actors in practical transdisciplinary research requires methodologies like co-design [9]. Both schools of thought share the foundation of both multidisciplinary (cooperation of researchers from multiple disciplines) and interdisciplinary (transfer of knowledge and methods between disciplines) research [9]. Today, the practical transdisciplinarity seems to have emerged as the predominant approach [10].

Within the context of THEIA^{XR}, we understand transdisciplinary co-design as an approach where multiple academic disciplines (engineering sciences, design, psychology, ELSA) as well as non-academic actors, primarily vehicle operators working in the use case domains of snow-grooming, container logistics and construction, are methodically collaborating in a design process and decision-making within that process at eye-level. The co-design process in THEIA^{XR} is driven by methods and principles of HCD (ISO 9241-210:2019) and scenario-based design [13], which are applied in a way to enable transdisciplinary collaboration.

2.2 Application of transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design

Scenarios are stories involving fictional actors in a sequence of actions and events which can be used to describe problems in current practice and possible solutions for them [13]. The scenario-based design framework [13] encompasses four phases, from the development of problem scenarios up to the final interaction scenarios outlining design specifications. The main benefits of scenarios are their concreteness (making problems and solutions easily graspable), flexibility (allowing for quick and easy creation and adjustment), the user perspective (focusing on user needs while mitigating representational bias or the researchers) and evocativeness (facilitating the reflection of design ideas) [13]. These features make scenario-based design ideal for transdisciplinary collaboration. In THEIA^{XR}, we adopted this framework, starting with the definition of the current situation of vehicle operation in each use case based on user research in T3.1 and iteratively suggesting, co-designing and validating ideas in workshops with operators and stakeholders from the use case domains (see **Table 1** and **Figure 1**).

Table 1: Stages of the transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design approach in THEIA^{XR}

Scenario type	Contents	Co-design participants*	Completion
Problem scenarios (T3.1, reported in D3.1/D3.6)	Current procedure of vehicle operation, handling of use case scenarios described in D2.2, hazards in the work environment	UC1: 6 operators UC2: 3 operators, 1 stakeholder UC3: 6 operators	UC1: 03/2023 UC2: 12/2023 UC3: 08/2023
Vision scenarios (T3.2, reported in D3.2)	Ideal futuristic scenario of vehicle operation, description of the use of planned technologies and functions	UC1: 5 operators, 5 stakeholders UC2: 2 operators, 1 stakeholder UC3: 12 operators	UC1: 02/2024 UC2: 11/2024 UC3: 05/2024
Information scenarios (T3.2)	Vision scenarios as a basis + information requirements of operators, conveyed by XR technologies and onboard monitors	UC1: 5 operators, 2 stakeholders UC2: 4 operators, 1 stakeholder UC3: 11 operators	UC1: 04/2025 UC2: 06/2025 UC3: 02/2025
Interaction scenarios (T3.2)	Information scenarios as a basis + critical interaction design recommendations for safety-relevant functions and interactions + integrated concepts for positive user experience (PUX) But: No full interaction scenarios by definition of [13] due to effort and scope limitations.	UC1: 4 operators UC2: 4 operators, 1 stakeholder UC3: 6 operators	UC1: 07/2025 UC2: 06/2025 UC3: 06/2025
*Not including THEIA ^{XR} consortium members			

In deliverable D3.1, we described how the prerequisite user research was conducted using contextual inquiries [14] and a variation of the critical incident technique [15]. The findings were used to create problem scenarios outlining the status quo of vehicle operation, providing easily graspable descriptions of how typical tasks are currently handled in each use case and how problematic or dangerous situations may arise. These problem scenarios would lay the foundation for the co-design of possible solutions and new technologies for vehicle operators.

However, it was assumed that operators may have difficulties coming up with solutions on their own and may both over- and underestimate what is currently technically possible. In an ideal transdisciplinary co-design setting involving both operators and engineering experts of the THEIA^{XR} consortium, it would be possible to incrementally suggest, explore and define technical solutions in an ongoing discussion. But it had to be expected that it would not always be possible to arrange such an ideal co-design setting for a number of reasons (schedule conflicts, too large effort to travel to workshop location, language barriers), and even if all necessary partners were present for a productive discussion of ideas, it may simply be too time-consuming to ideate suitable and feasible solutions for all parts of the problem scenarios from scratch. It was considered sensible to start into transdisciplinary co-design with an initial collection of ideas that could be used both as a starting point for the exploration of technical solutions and as a reference for what is technically feasible within the scope of the project. Thus, consortium-internal ideation workshops were conducted in each use case to collect and assess initial technology ideas that could improve the current situation described in the problem scenarios. The ideas considered useful and feasible were then integrated into activity scenarios [13] outlining how we envision vehicle operation in the future. We internally call these scenarios “vision scenarios”.

Figure 1: Visualisation of transdisciplinary inputs and results of the co-design process

During an internal review of the initial ideation workshop’s results, the spectrum of ideas was found to be focused on solutions that emphasize projections and screen displays. To include some more speculative ideas emphasizing HMD use as well (which may currently not be accepted by a majority of vehicle operators), we created two vision scenarios for each use case, one realistic version aimed at matching the technologies already in development and being more readily acceptable, and one futuristic version aimed at being more ambitious (heavily emphasizing HMD use) while possibly being less acceptable for operators and partly out of scope for actual implementation in the project. Since the realistic vision scenarios are based on the use case scenarios and technology specifications (see D2.2), they were prioritized.

The initial vision scenarios based on internal ideation were discussed, expanded and validated in several co-design workshops with operators, advancing through the stages of scenario-based design (see **Table 1**). In the co-design of vision scenarios, we conducted two workshops in UC1, UC2 and UC3 each, for a total number of 10 non-consortium participants in UC1, 4 non-consortium participants in UC2 and 12 non-consortium participants in UC3. In the following co-design of information scenarios, we again conducted two workshops in both UC1 and UC3 each, for a total number of 7 non-consortium participants in UC1, 5 non-consortium participants in UC2 and 11 non-consortium participants in UC3. The information scenarios are complemented by sketches and wireframes of the planned information architecture and design, supporting the technical partners associated with each use case in the HMI development for the respective prototypes.

Following the completion of information scenarios, the final phase of scenario-based co-design was the creation and validation of interaction scenarios. It must be noted that back in the proposal phase and in the first version of this deliverable, interaction scenarios as defined in the scenario-based design process of [13] were intended to be the outcome of this final deliverable. This type of scenario would contain detailed

descriptions of user input and system output procedures which can serve as design specifications for prototype development. However, as the project progressed, it became clear that the effort to adequately develop and validate vision and information scenarios was much greater than expected, also due to more limited vehicle operator availability than anticipated, and it would likely not be possible to complete and validate full interaction scenarios in the given time frame of the project. Furthermore, due to the technology concept exploration in the focus of this project, it seems overly ambitious to create complete interaction scenarios, essentially detailed design specifications, for systems with a much greater scope and complexity than the three use case scenarios per use case (as detailed in deliverable D2.5) suggest. Thus, it was decided internally to limit the interaction scenario expansion to safety-critical interactions, highlighting parts of the information scenarios where specific recommendations and rules should apply to avoid confusion, misunderstandings of information or the (accidental or intentional) deactivation of critical safety warnings, possibly resulting in threat to life for the vehicle operator, co-workers or bystanders.

Beyond solutions that aim to improve safety and efficiency, the perception of self-efficacy, meaningfulness of work and other sources positive user experience (PUX) based on psychological need fulfilment are important goals of co-design in THEIA^{XR}. PUX concepts were ideated and validated in 2025 and integrated into the interaction scenarios to illustrate possible future ways how positive experiences at work can be conveyed in the use cases.

3 Contributions throughout the project

3.1 Value-sensitive co-design

Our investigation of the end-users' privacy and other ethical needs was framed around concepts of "privacy-by-design" and "value-sensitive design". The privacy by design approach is the main leading framework, used in the European Union (https://www.edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/subjects/privacy-design_en). It emphasizes the idea that privacy considerations should be put at the core of the development procedure, not just added in the last moment to fulfil regulatory requirements. To start our investigation into the problem of privacy aspects of work, we incorporated questions about privacy and data ownership perception into the initial interviews with the end-user stakeholders of the project. However, during the following analysis of the literature about different caveats of the working practices and origins of privacy-by-design approach, we realized that the project should not just concentrate solemnly on the privacy questions, but also take into account the more general considerations about users' values: the things, which represent the high-level concepts, matters to the end-users.

To conduct our investigations in the following direction, we applied the value-sensitive design. This approach focused on the significance of human values throughout the full cycle of the design and engineering process and specifically pointed to the fact that technology development should consider the values of the end-user [16]. The approach it is widely used in projects involving multiple stakeholders and partners, such as technological development in engineering and information systems design [16], [17], [18], because it helps identify high-level positions and points to potential contradictions between stakeholders (so-called "value conflicts")[19]. For example, in the healthcare domain, the end-users' privacy values can contradict the healthcare providers' values of better, more complete information gathering in the sake of potentially better treatment. Similarly, on the construction side, the needs/values of security (and therefore - desire to create better surveillance mechanisms and step-by-step checklists) can clash with users' desires for privacy and autonomy at work. As values are, by definition, high-level concepts, value analysis should be conducted from the early stages of project development and involves an iterative process of clarifying how to a) better embody certain values in the developed technology and b) search for technological solutions that optimize outcomes in cases of conflicting stakeholder values [19]. Value-sensitive design does not force practitioners to choose some specific method to discover and evaluate the stakeholders' values (it can be previous works, preliminary interviews, group discussions with the stakeholders, etc). In our case, we used two models of values, which seem to be relevant in the working process, were applied in the framework of a scenario-based co-design approach: Schwartz Theory of basic values (which we reinterpreted in work-related context), and expanded TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) as related to understanding the context of use and related to engineering values proposed by [20]. We also added safety as a core engineering value and enjoyment into the TAM, as they are often associated with the willingness to adopt novel technology, particularly in the XR domain [21].

The original Schwartz approach identifies core human values as ten main concepts: benevolence, universalism, self-direction (autonomy), achievement, stimulation, hedonism, security, conformity, tradition, and power [22]. As Schwartz values are widely used in various contexts (including the context of values in work), we followed the previous works in the domain and developed a short questionnaire based on the Short Schwartz's Value Survey [23] and the Values at Work Scale [24]. We used this 10-item questionnaire to facilitate discussions with operators, and it was qualitatively validated via group discussion process (we plan to make the quantitative validation of the questionnaire in the future; however, as a general psychometric instrument, the full validation is beyond the goals of the project).

As the scenario-based approach is one of the core methods for values representation and values elicitation method [25], we applied it in each stage of our work. First, following [26], we used a scenario-based approach to elicit the users' key values and bring them into the following co-design practices with stakeholders. For this, we concentrated on co-discussing the persona of the engaged operator, which was created before in

the frames of the main problem scenario (e.g. for helping the operators evaluate proposed technologies). We asked operators to discuss the Schwartz values in the prism of the things, important for this engaged operator and extrapolate them to everyday working context (which working processes and everyday activities are guided by the main operator's values); Secondly, we applied an extended TAM-based value evaluation paradigm to the prototypes of technological solutions co-developed through the previous stages of problem scenarios. In this part, we asked participants to reflect on the technology's potential positive and negative effects, including ethical drawbacks of potential dependency on technology and the balance between safety and efficiency. Results of both evaluations and more detailed information about the developed methods and the practical assessment of values can be found in D3.3.

Finally, based on the reflection of the operators, we formulated four dimensions, which should be further explored in relation to our technological proposals: problem of autonomy on work, problem of security and overreliance, problem of disruption of social working context and enjoyment and over-automation of the tasks. Based on these 4 problems, we created 4 anti-scenarios (what the work could look like if we do not support these values during our design and implementation stage) and ask operators to reflect on these scenarios in terms of feasibility, potential outcomes and preventive measures. The work will be presented in the coming deliverable D3.8. Finally, we are planning to use the extracted problems and anti-scenarios to create a large-scale vignette experiment on the crowdsourcing Prolific platform, where we'll vary the consequences of core values violations and protective measurements participants envision for preventing/mitigating anti-scenarios. The results of this evaluation will also be presented in D3.8.

3.2 Haptic control and feedback function ideation and design

Early drafts of the realistic and futuristic vision scenarios for all use cases were used as a basis for ideating functional specifications for the control and feedback functions to be designed in the scope of the THEIA^{XR} project. Since these scenarios contain sequential descriptions of sets of control actions and information feedback components which, although they are ideal for providing a general sense of what the final application may look or feel like to an end-user, remain relatively vague from a technical perspective, we proceeded as follows: First, we decomposed scenarios into component actions and events. Here the aim was to isolate individual tasks performed by the user or by the machine in order to identify and eliminate duplicates of tasks. Second, we further decomposed identified actions and events into component control and feedback functions. At this level, the temporal sequence is completely ignored and only a list of non-overlapping individual control and feedback functions, formulated such that they provide a clear idea of the general requirements for the function considered. Then, we grouped identical functions to eliminate overlaps. Finally, we ideated function details and drafted technical specification. At this level, the formulation is almost entirely abstracted from the context of use and focuses solely on the technical realization of the identified control or feedback function. The resulting functional specification is discussed in detail in deliverable D4.4. This process will be repeated shortly with the final versions of the scenarios presented in this deliverable, so as to converge towards a final functional specification for deliverable D4.4.

Contrary to visual and auditory feedback, haptics is an information communication medium which remains largely unfamiliar to many people outside of the field, and whose properties are difficult to accurately convey through verbal or text descriptions. For this reason, Haption chose to leverage the opportunity provided by on-site workshops with snow groomer operators at the Prinoth headquarters in Sterzing in February 2024 to organize a demonstration workshop on haptics prior to the actual co-design workshops (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Haptics demos during the workshops in Sterzing (February 2024)

These workshops featured a general presentation regarding the scope of haptic feedback technologies with various examples tailored to the potential applications to the snow grooming use case. They were followed by a demonstration session of a 6DoF force feedback device (Haption Virtuose 6D) interacting with a simulated environment, which allowed rendering of virtual spring and viscous forces, virtual handled masses, collisions with virtual objects as well as guidance along predefined trajectories in 3D space. The rationale behind these workshops was to provide stakeholders, in particular operators, with an intuitive feel for what such feedback could enable in the context of UC1. In the following workshops, we also administered the haptics-specific questionnaire shown in **Table 2**. to obtain precise feedback on operator’s expectations regarding haptic feedback.

Table 2: General questionnaire regarding opportunities for using haptics in the different use cases

Question key	Question
Q1	Are there any situations in your work where you think that receiving vibration notifications through the handles of the joysticks may be of value?
Q2	If so, should vibration in the joystick be rather used for confirming that things are working as intended, to warn of things going wrong, or equally for both?
Q3	Would you rather see such vibration feedback as a function that is switched on permanently, or something that you would activate only when you feel you need it?
Q4	Are there any situations in your work where you think that force-feedback guidance through the joysticks could help you perform better, or make tasks easier?
Q5	If such force feedback was implemented, would you rather see it as a function that is switched on permanently, or something that you would activate only when you feel you need it?
Q6	If a joystick were to be developed that featured more than 2 degrees of freedom, would you be open to the use of different, possibly more intuitive, control patterns for the vehicle tool positions and motions in space? If so, do you have any specific ideas in mind?

The specifics of the feedback components which may benefit from haptics are discussed in detail in deliverable D4.4. Below are the broad conclusions that emerged from these questionnaires.

Table 3: General conclusions from the discussions around the haptics questionnaires in UC1

Question key	Conclusion key	Conclusion
Q1	C1.1	Tactile feedback is generally perceived as a potentially helpful form of feedback, if adequately implemented. In particular, notifying the operator of events appears to be the most promising field of application.
	C1.2	Any vibration feedback providing warnings related to a tool's functions should be co-located on the handle of the control device used to operate said tool.
Q2	C2.1	Operators unanimously agree that vibration feedback should be used exclusively for warnings (things going wrong) to avoid sensory clutter.
	C2.2	If used for warnings, tactile feedback should be used sparingly with a focus on warnings for higher-severity events. This is because a certain number of unusual events are "normal" in everyday operation and should not cause sensory clutter.
Q3	C3.1	Tactile feedback should be a toggleable function. However, it is acceptable to have it activated by default.
Q4	C4.1	Force feedback is generally perceived as a potentially helpful form of feedback, in particular when it comes to guiding the operator's motion towards a predefined target. Which tools and targets specifically could benefit from guidance is a subject of debate among operators.
	C4.2	It should always be possible to override the force provided by the force feedback system relatively easily, mainly for safety reasons.
	C4.3	Force feedback should not be used to dynamically adjust the perceived mechanical properties of the joystick, since operators rely on the assumptions that these are constant to perform their work.
Q5	C5.1	Force feedback should be a toggleable function, both for safety reasons and for user comfort. However, it is acceptable to have it activated by default.
Q6	C6.1	Operators are open to the idea of different input device kinematics, however there is little consensus on what could work. The general opinion is that if novel input kinematics can be proposed, they should be, and decisions on the viability of these ideas should be taken after preliminary testing by several operators.
OTHER	C7.1	Haptics is perceived as a form of feedback which would likely mostly benefit novice operators (applies to tactile feedback for notifying of unusual situations, as well as force feedback for guiding motions).

While Haption is not directly involved in the excavator use case (UC3), there is some overlap between the functions discussed in UC1 and UC2 and those discussed in UC3. For this reason, we reiterated the questionnaires during UC3 operator workshops in March and April 2024. However, this time no practical demos were presented prior, only a short presentation on haptics was given to operators prior to the administration of the questionnaires. Operators' responses generally confirmed the conclusions obtained in the UC1 workshops, in particular conclusions C1.1, C2.1, C3.1, C4.1, C5.1 and C7.1 (see **Table 3**). This confirms our initial intuition about potential overlaps in the use cases and provides perspectives for broader application of the envisioned haptic feedback functions beyond the use cases specifically considered within the project.

4 Final integrated interaction scenarios

4.1 UC1: Snow-grooming

In preparation of the co-design phase, an ideation workshop was held in October 2023 to collect suggestions for technologies and concepts that may be of interest to snow groomer operators and mitigate the problems and environmental threats detailed in deliverable D3.1/D3.6 (final). After collection, the ideas were evaluated by the consortium partners in terms of technical feasibility and usefulness (output) for the operators. As is shown in **Figure 3**, the evaluation resulted in all the discussed technologies and functions to be considered mostly feasible and useful. Based on the feedback of Prinoth representatives, only functions involving XR headsets (see bottom right notes in **Figure 3**) were discarded due to the high risk of causing motion sickness, which already poses a risk particularly in this use case even without a headset.

Figure 3: Screenshot of UC1 ideation workshop results

Summarized, this resulted in the following feature ideas that were integrated in the initial vision scenario:

- Ambient light bars around the windscreen, which indicate vehicle health during startup, and possibly also height of the blade above soil (to avoid tearing up the soil beneath snow surface)
- Recognition (and visualisation) of target slope area for grooming based on digital slope model
- Laser projection of auxiliary lines and a grid for assessing vehicle dimensions, overlap with previously groomed lanes and depth of the snow in front of the vehicle
- 3D Visualisation of current vehicle position and alignment on the slope on system screen
- Detection of objects (snow cannons, vehicles, persons) in the vicinity of the vehicle. Detected objects are displayed on the screen and conveyed by a ambient light and acoustic warnings
- Guidance system indicating a safe way to a set waypoint (during snowstorm)

These ideas were validated and expanded during co-design workshops in Sterzing, Italy, in February 2024. Most of the ideas were approved and expanded by operators with minor changes or comments. The only function not approved was a new idea suggested later in the process regarding visual feedback on ideal speed for best snow preparation results. Furthermore, there was ambiguous feedback regarding the feasibility and usefulness of the visualization of ideal blade and tiller settings based on sensor and/or visual camera readings. It was discussed that blade and tiller settings are evaluated and adjusted by operators while driving entirely based on the appearance of the snow surface in front of- and behind the vehicle. It was determined that any function that could assist operators with this task would likely need to involve AI image processing technology based on a large data corpus of slope surface images and video material. The required effort to pursue such functions relying heavily on AI further was agreed to be too great and out of scope for a project focused on XR technology.

An interim version of the operator-validated vision scenarios was presented in the first version of this deliverable, D3.2. For the next phase of information scenario co-design, two more co-design workshops involving Prinoth snow groomer operators and stakeholders were held in May and November 2024. In these workshops, information requirements and ideas for visualizations and data depictions in the cabin were collected and discussed. Based on this input, information architecture and design concepts for projections on the snow in front of the vehicle, ambient light bars in the wind screen frame and tablet screens inside the cabin were developed. The concepts were presented to snow groomer operators, discussed and validated in two more workshops in April and July 2025.

During the visits in November 2024 and April 2025, workshops and interviews concerning positive experiences at work and the perception of meaning at work were conducted as well. Based on their findings, concepts for positive user experience (PUX) specifically for UC1 were first ideated by the HdM-internal team and then also validated with a group of experienced snow groomer operators in the visit in July 2025.

In **Table 4**, we present the final integrated interaction scenario for UC1, expanding the interim vision scenarios from D3.2 with descriptions of the conceptual sources and use of information. The descriptions are complemented by operator-validated wireframes and drafts in the first column, which present an idea of how the information requirements of the operators could be met by a future system. These wireframes present concepts, not polished interface designs, and should not be understood as the only possible solution. Text passages marked in blue represent operator-validated PUX concepts, which are commented in the third column. Text passages marked in yellow represent safety-critical functions or procedures that require careful handling or specific rules in terms of interaction design to avoid danger. Recommendations for the interaction design of these functions and procedures are also added in the third column.

Table 4: Validated UC1 interaction scenario

Visualization (Exemplary for selected technologies and functions, not matching the scenario descriptions in their entirety)	Scenario Yellow: Safety-critical elements and procedures Blue: Integrated concepts for positive user experience (PUX)	Additional comments on marked passages Yellow: Design recommendations Blue: Explanation of PUX concepts
<p>Figure 4: Snow groomer leaving the garage</p>	<p>Introduction</p> <p>Marco is an experienced snow groomer operator and has been preparing slopes for more than ten years.</p> <p>As he arrives at the ski slope’s valley station in the late afternoon, Marco meets with several other snow groomer operators, and they quickly discuss who will take responsibility for which parts of the slope.</p> <p>Today Marco will use a machine outfitted with the “THEIA” safety and assistance system. Despite being very proficient at his job even without assistance, knowing that he can rely on the system makes him feel more at ease today, since he has heard about heavy snowfall being expected later that night. Once the slope is closed for visitors, Marco and his colleagues head out to the garage where the snow groomers are parked (see Figure 4).</p>	
<p>Figure 5: Light feedback indicates that vehicle is operational</p>	<p>Preparations and planning</p> <p>Marco carries out a brief inspection on the outside of the machine, enters the cabin and starts the engine and electronic systems. On his right-hand side there is a system monitor for most of the important information about the vehicle, the slope and the task. As the system is starting, the frame of the monitor glows green, indicating that all the vehicle’s mechatronic and electric systems are operational and there are no major issues (see Figure 5). In addition, the system displays a checklist for all the routine safety inspections and maintenance tasks that have to be done by the operator manually. Marco confirms that he has already completed the visual inspection from outside and ticks off the other inspections inside the cabin as he completes them.</p>	<p>PUX concept: Immediate feedback on the vehicle’s operational readiness, reducing mental load and avoiding that any checks are forgotten or done more often than needed. Approved by three out of four operators.</p>

Figure 6: Weather forecast showing fog on the slope

Once all checks are complete, Marco opens the weather forecast page in the system, which shows precipitation, fog and general visibility on a topological map of the slope (see Figure 6). He inspects the recorded weather events and precipitation in the past two hours to gain an idea of the snow's quality up on the slope right now and then checks the expected precipitation and visibility on the slope over the course of the next six hours. This allows Marco to think about the ideal speed and tiller settings in advance as well as planning an ideal route for his shift to avoid having to groom the same area twice due to intense snowfall.

The map also shows him real-time data such as wind and fog information from sensors on stationary snow cannons.

Lastly, Marco checks an additional feature that shows an estimated number of visitors that have been on the slope today and a forecast on the expected number of visitors on the next day. He sees that around 3.000 visitors have been on the slope since the morning, which tells him that a lot of snow will have been carried down by the skiers over the course of the day. Furthermore, he sees that several school classes are expected to visit the slope tomorrow for a skiing course, which reminds him of one of the reasons why he chose this job – making skiing fun and safe for everyone, especially the young guests.

PUX concept: Estimation of past and expected visitors on the slope to convey the meaningfulness and concrete impact of slope preparation beyond being just a job. Approved by two out of four operators.

Figure 7: Map screen showing restricted areas

Start of snow grooming (build slope matching target surface)

Once done with checking the weather information, Marco switches to the regular real-time map view and activates the top-down angle, showing his vehicle in the centre and realistic depictions of the environment, other vehicles and known structures around him.

As he drives out of the garage, the THEIA system projects guidance lines on the ground in front of the vehicle indicating the dimensions of the tiller in the back to avoid collisions while moving in tight spaces. The vehicle slowly moves out of the garage and into the open.

On the map screen Marco can show or hide different areas: his own working area, temporarily restricted areas due to winch operations by other operators and danger zones that will turn into these kind of areas, general restricted areas defined by the slope park administration, and already prepared areas (see Figure 7). Further information he can show or hide are navigation instructions, lanes, and winch anchors. He could also change the colours of all these areas on the monitor but leaves the default setting for now.

Since one of the winch operation areas overlaps with Marco's planned route up the hill, he checks which of his colleagues is operating the snow groomer there and uses the call-function to ask if he can pass through that area safely.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

The visualization of the tiller's dimensions in the back must reliably match its position and angle in real time.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

While it may be possible to toggle the visibility of certain areas in the 3D map, restricted (dangerous) areas must always be visible to avoid potential danger to life.

As Marco approaches and passes through the temporarily restricted area under his colleague's guidance, the THEIA system emits a warning sound, the joystick vibrates and the light bars around the wind screen glow up yellow. Had Marco not already recognized the restricted area and contacted his colleague, he would have been warned about moving into a potentially dangerous area now. While moving up the slope and grooming his first lane, Marco quickly checks the tank level among the permanently visible vehicle status metrics on the bottom of the screen, and the weather forecast for the next hour, which is indicated in the top right corner of the map monitor.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

While operators may be enabled to configure the specific feedback provided by the machine in case of warnings (audio, vibration, lights), critical warnings must never be entirely suppressible.

Figure 8: Light feedback and projection warning of blade being set too low

Marco activates a snow depth visualisation system projecting a point grid onto the snow, with larger light dots indicating a lot of surplus snow in front of the vehicle. This allows Marco to adjust the blade and keep his eyes on the snow surface without having to check the snow measurement system screen in the front of the cabin between his feet.

As he routinely checks the side mirrors while grooming the slope uphill, the lower windshield light bar and the display frame lights flash yellow and the joystick gives specific haptic feedback to warn him that the blade is currently too low, which could cause the soil beneath the snow to get torn up. An arrow symbol projected onto the snow in front of him also shows him that the blade is too low (see Figure 8). Marco recognizes the warning and immediately pulls the blade up slightly. Similarly, warnings about too high vehicle speed or too high tiller pressure are also conveyed by yellow ambient light feedback, haptic feedback and more details on the main monitor.

Critical interaction design recommendation: Certain colours, sounds or haptic feedback patterns must only be used for critical warnings. For example, the light bars in the cabin should only flash red if a person or object is nearby (colour coding from yellow to orange to red to indicate distance from the vehicle) or when approaching restricted areas.

Figure 9: Projections of lane borders (blue), restricted (red) and completed areas (green)

Limited vision / zero-sight navigation

Night falls and heavy snowfall sets in, limiting the vision to only about ten metres and obscuring the snow surface. This makes it very hard for Marco to recognize the lanes he has already prepared and the overlap he needs to create with them. Thus, Marco activates the "poor visibility support" of the THEIA system. Bright and clear laser lines and symbols are now being projected on the ground in front of the vehicle, highlighting the borders of the previously groomed lanes, already completed areas and restricted areas (see Figure 9). Marco switches to the 3D view on his monitor, which shows the vehicle and its surroundings in a slightly angled 3D top-down perspective.

As he glances at the onboard snow measurement system, he can also see the real-time position and alignment of his vehicle on the slope in a realistic 3D view, helping him recognize which area of the slope he is in while driving.

As Marco unknowingly approaches a stationary snow cannon concealed by the heavy snowfall, a collision warning sign and the real-time distance of the object is being projected on the snow surface in front of the vehicle. Warnings are also shown on the monitor. The light bars around the windshield also glow yellow, turning orange and red as the vehicle gets closer to the object. Lines projected around the snow cannon by the THEIA system indicate the minimum safe distance for Marco to pass it.

As the night progresses, the snowstorm turns even heavier and for a while, Marco can barely see the environment around him at all. Back in the days before the new assistance system was fit on his snow groomer, this would have forced him to stop and wait. But thanks to the accurate real-time display of the vehicle's position, alignment and movement on the 3D map and the laser projections in front of him indicating the border of his previous lane, he can now keep going slowly.

Critical interaction design recommendation: The 3D representation of the vehicle and any known structures on the slope must be accurate, real-time and stable. Any inaccuracies could result in a loss of trust in this system and void its core purpose. Should the accuracy and stability of the system not be guaranteed at any time, the operator needs to be informed.

Figure 10: Winch-operation-based restricted area on the map screen (red)

The snowfall has subsided, and Marco approaches a steep part of the slope where he needs to use the winch. He slowly drives towards the upper edge of the slope, gets out of the vehicle and attaches the winch cable to the anchor point. Then he re-enters the vehicle, where he confirms the winch operation in the system. In the 3D map the anchor point is automatically highlighted, the area between the anchor and the snow groomer is marked as temporarily restricted and the area below the snow groomer is marked as potential danger zone for his colleagues to see (see Figure 10). He then slowly descends the slope in the vehicle. While using the winch, Marco pays particular attention to any moving objects around him, since the vehicle itself and especially the winch cable are great dangers to approaching skiers who may still be coming down the slope from the ski huts above, despite the slope already being closed.

Critical interaction design recommendation: Starting a winch operation should automatically set the respective anchor point on the 3D map. Powering the vehicle off and on again during the winch operation must result in the previous winch anchor point being restored, not replaced at the current position of the vehicle.

Figure 11: Critical warning of imminent collision

Figure 12: Skier highlighted on map screen

Winch operation and object warning (collision avoidance)

And indeed a few skiers pass behind the vehicle in some distance, being highlighted by the light bars around the wind screen with green spots indicating their current position and relatively safe distance from the vehicle. At one point however, a quickly moving red spot appears on the light bars, followed by all of them flashing red as a critical warning, accompanied by an audio warning from the speakers, a notice on the monitor and a stop sign being projected on the ground in front of the vehicle, alerting Marco immediately (see Figure 11). He stops the machine and looks into the direction where the red area had appeared. A lone, seemingly drunk skier descends the slope right next to the snow groomer. Marco sighs and waits for them to pass. The skier is also being highlighted on the map screen, allowing Marco to track their position until they are in a safe distance (see Figure 12). As the skier passes the vehicle, the red spot moves from the lower left to the upper left corner of the windscreen frame light bars and changes from red to orange, conveying their position and movement. Once they are at a safe distance, the colour eventually changes to green and then the coloured spot disappears. This lets Marco know that it is safe to resume grooming the slope.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

The system should generally not interfere with the operator's actions, but should a person be detected in the immediate vicinity of the vehicle, it must be stopped to avoid possibly lethal accidents.

PUX concept: While being a main safety feature, the person and object detection also contributes to the feeling of safety, avoiding that skiers or skidoos near the vehicle could be overlooked, taking away cognitive load and stress. Approved by two out of four operators.

	<p>End of first shift Marco's first shift is nearing its end, but snowfall has intensified again, reducing his vision to around ten metres in front of him. Marco reactivates the visibility support system and enables the navigation system, showing him a safe path to the hut where his colleagues are waiting, both on the 3D map screen and the projections in front of the vehicle.</p> <p>As Marco slowly approaches the hut, he checks the progress bar for his part of the slope today. He sees that due to the snowstorm, he has been slower than expected and completed a bit less than half of his assigned area so far, resulting in an estimated completion by 1:30am at night at the current pace. However, he estimates that once the snowstorm has subsided, he will be able to make up for some of the lost time.</p>	<p>PUX concept: Estimation of the current progress and completion time to convey self-efficacy and plannability. Approved by three out of four operators. It is important that supervisors cannot access this information, since that could lead to pressure on the operators, resulting in negative feelings.</p>
	<p>End of workday In his second, rather uneventful shift, Marco has made quick progress. Now, around 1:15am, he returns to the garage.</p> <p>Before logging off the system and powering off the machine, he is presented with a screen showing him a "replay of the day", a fast-forward video recording from the vehicle's front camera that shows how he groomed the slope today, also documenting the blade and tiller settings over the course of time and highlighting the moments when the THEIA warning system got triggered. Marco exports the video recording to his smartphone so that he can show it to his daughter, who loves watching her father's adventures. He also plans to show one specific part where he was using the winch on a steep area of the slope to a new colleague of his, who is still struggling with learning the ideal settings. With the video, he can explain his own procedure based on real events.</p> <p>Finally, Marco exits the vehicle, looking forward to returning home.</p>	<p>PUX concept: Video recording containing additional machine information; both for learning and self-improvement purposes and for sharing the experience with friends and family (connectedness). Approved by three out of four operators. As mentioned above, supervisors should not be able to access this information.</p>

4.2 UC2: Logistics

In preparation of the co-design phase, an ideation workshop was held in December 2023 to collect suggestions for technologies and concepts that may be of interest to reach stacker operators and mitigate the problems and environmental threats detailed in deliverable D3.1/D3.6 (final). After collection, the ideas were evaluated by the consortium partners in terms of technical feasibility and usefulness (output) for the operators. As is shown in **Figure 13**, the evaluation resulted most of the discussed technologies and functions to be considered feasible and useful. One idea to the left of the board in **Figure 13** related to the use of camera-equipped drones to provide mobile camera perspectives for reach stacker remote control was considered to present too great difficulty and effort.

Figure 13: Screenshot of UC2 ideation workshop results

Summarized, this resulted in the following feature ideas that were integrated in the initial vision scenario:

- Navigation to target location on harbour terminal
- Detection of objects (people, vehicles) in the vicinity of the vehicle or within the working area. Detected objects are displayed on the screen. If an object enters the working area, the vehicle operator's attention is drawn by a warning signal from the ambient lights and an acoustic signal
- XR-assisted container pick-up and placement, indicating correct spreader alignment with container and twist lock status
- XR visualisation of container dimensions and projected turning areas on ground to avoid collisions
- Use of haptic feedback and control functions to convey weight and assist with spreader placement

Up to the first submission date, it had not been possible to validate and expand these ideas with actual reach stacker operators due to still ongoing contact establishment and recruitment efforts in UC2. It was possible to observe and interview two test drivers of KALMAR in their vehicles on a test area in Ljungby, Sweden, for user research (see deliverable D3.1/3.6), however, test drivers alone would not suffice for the subsequent

co-design stages. As of July 2024, a new support partner has been acquired for participation in UC2 co-design. The ideas above were validated and expanded in online co-design workshops in July and October 2024. All of the ideas were approved and expanded by operators.

An interim version of the operator-validated vision scenarios was presented in the first version of this deliverable, D3.2. For the next phase of information scenario co-design, two more online co-design workshops involving reach stacker operators and stakeholders from Hanko, Finland, were held in October and December 2024. In these workshops, information requirements and ideas for visualizations and data depictions in the cabin were collected and discussed. However, UC2 comes with the added difficulty of remote-control workstations being highly configurable and not limited to any single layout of screens. Thus, another workshop was held in June 2025 to allocate information requirements to specific tasks and areas of an ideal remote-control screen setup.

Based on conversations in the workshops in October and December 2024, concepts for positive user experience (PUX) specifically for UC2 were first ideated by the HdM-internal team and then also validated with a group of experienced reach stacker operators a second the online-workshop in June 2025.

In **Table 5**, we present the final integrated interaction scenario for UC2, expanding the interim vision scenarios from D3.2 with descriptions of the conceptual sources and use of information. The descriptions are complemented by operator-validated wireframes and drafts in the first column, which present an idea of how the information requirements of the operators could be met by a future system. These wireframes present concepts, not polished interface designs, and should not be understood as the only possible solution. Text passages marked in blue represent operator-validated PUX concepts, which are commented in the third column. Text passages marked in yellow represent safety-critical functions or procedures that require careful handling or specific rules in terms of interaction design to avoid danger. Recommendations for the interaction design of these functions and procedures are also added in the third column.

Table 5: Validated UC2 interaction scenario

Visualization (Exemplary for selected technologies and functions, not matching the scenario descriptions in their entirety)	Scenario ■ Yellow: Safety-critical elements and procedures ■ Blue: Integrated concepts for positive user experience (PUX)	Additional comments on marked passages ■ Yellow: Design recommendations ■ Blue: Explanation of PUX concepts
<p>Figure 14: Ideal distribution of information on RC desk setup (workshop result)</p>	<p>Introduction</p> <p>Matias, a newly trained reach stacker operator, is on his way to the remote-control office in Sweden, from where he operates reach stackers in various harbour terminals around the world. Once arrived, he sits down at his control desk with four large screens in front of him, a smaller screen in the centre between the joysticks and another smaller one on the left-hand side of the joysticks on the desk (see Figure 14). He logs into the system and selects his assigned harbour terminal at a small port in southern Finland. A current weather forecast of the selected location pops up in the large middle screen. After checking it, Mathias closes the forecast.</p>	
	<p>The screens display different kinds of information that Matias needs for his daily work. The information can be individually organized on the screens as desired by every operator and stored for later use. Mathias has done this a while ago and has the following setup: The large screen in the middle shows the front view of the reach stacker including projections of container dimensions on the ground if relevant. In addition, the wind speed in metres per second is always visible on this screen. The two large screens on the left and right show the side views of the machine, equivalent to the rearview mirrors. On the top large screen Mathias sees different views that he can modify and that automatically change depending on the current task. These are different camera views of the vehicle as well as a terminal map. All camera views also show nearby objects. The screen also shows the light bar (traffic lights), which signalizes the status of the spreader's twist locks when handling a container. The small screen between the joysticks shows the rear view of the machine. On the left small screen Mathias sees the machine status, container info, truck info, warnings.</p>	

	<p>Since his job list from that terminal today requires a certain loading capacity, he selects a reach stacker with matching specifications. The THEIA remote control system highlights the machine on a map view of the port, showing its current parked position inside a garage. Matias inspects the details of the machine and confirms that he wants to connect to it for today's work.</p> <p>The system connects to the vehicle, showing a stable connection with minimal latency and a notification that the vehicle will be halted automatically should the connection ever suffer from too high latency or be lost. The connection stability is displayed by colour coding in the top right corner of the large display in the top. The radio, which can be used for communication, and the microphone for communicating with truck drivers, are turned on and off using physical buttons to the right and left of the joysticks.</p>	<p>Critical interaction design recommendation: The operator needs to know what happens in case of a disconnect or high latency.</p>
<p>Figure 15: Vehicle as seen through an outside camera on the port (image: VTT)</p>	<p>Preparations and planning</p> <p>Matias starts the safety inspection. On the screen, the outside camera view of the vehicle appears, made possible by several Pan-Tilt-Zoom-cameras installed in the vehicle garage and outside on structures around the whole port (see Figure 15). Additionally, there is a list of all the safety checks that have to be done manually by the remote operator and those that can be done automatically based on machine data and sensor readings. Matias switches between several cameras, sometimes swivelling them and zooming in on certain parts of the vehicle, and then confirms that there are no damages to the tires, no oil or fuel leaks and no ice on the critical places, ticking off these checks in the list. The reports feature automatically pops up on the left large screen. He checks for any maintenance comments or warnings about the vehicle from other operators or maintenance personnel but only finds a note that an urgent repair on the lights has been completed since the last time the vehicle was used. Finally, light feedback around the screen indicates that all checks have been completed and the vehicle is ready for operation.</p>	<p>PUX concept: Immediate feedback on the vehicle's operational readiness, reducing mental load and avoiding that any checks are forgotten or done more often than needed. Not specifically validated in this use case but approved by operators in UC1 and UC3.</p>

<p>Figure 16: Cabin view of the vehicle (image: VTT)</p>	<p>Matias now enters the cabin view (see Figure 16) and hears the real sound of the engine and the muffled beeping of vehicles outside the garage in his headphones, picked up by microphones in the reach stacker cabin. Several toggleable alternative camera views, a map view of the terminal, a dashboard of the vehicle's parameters (e. g., machine speed, boom and spreader positions, fuel or battery status, oil temperature, gearbox temperature) and a list of available jobs are available on the smaller monitor.</p>	<p>Critical interaction design recommendation: Operators need to be able to hear and feel the real environment of the machine as much as possible to get immersed despite the remote-control setup, "feel" the vehicle, perceive engine and component stress and other possible sources of danger.</p>
	<p>As Matias steers the reach stacker out of the garage, he selects the first job on the list. The current container location and its target location are displayed on the map view. After confirming the selection, he immediately sees a directional indicator appearing on the main screen, showing the ideal route and distance to the target container. Matias does not yet know the layout of this part of the port by heart but quickly finds the optimal path with the help of the navigation system on the screen.</p>	
	<p>While driving to the target container, moving green bars on the borders of the main screen indicate the relative position and proximity of objects and other vehicles moving around him, conveying distance via colour and size. After turning around a corner, Matias hears a warning sound and notices a bright orange area moving on the bottom border of the main screen, as well as a matching orange dot on the map view behind his vehicle. He checks the back camera view, seeing that a colleague is driving his reach stacker directly behind him before he takes another turn and disappears behind a stack of containers.</p>	<p>Critical interaction design recommendation: While operators may be enabled to configure the specific feedback provided by the machine in case of warnings (audio, vibration, lights), critical warnings must never be entirely suppressible.</p>

Figure 17: Spreader placement guidance (image: VTT)

Figure 18: Spreader placement guidance (image: VTT)

Figure 19: Navigation to target truck (image: VTT)

Container pick-up from– and placement on the ground

Finally, Matias arrives at his destination, which is also indicated by the target container being highlighted in the augmented camera view. As he approaches the container from the front, the container number is being verified by an optical character recognition system. After successful identification, visual feedback for the completed verification of the container is being virtually displayed along with its expected weight directly on its front.

Matias begins to move the spreader into a suitable working position. The horizontal and vertical distance between the spreader's twist locks and the corners of the container are visualized by the XR assistance system on the container surface (see Figure 17 and Figure 18). Matias focuses on these projections, which make it easier to find the correct position of the spreader. He lowers the spreader down towards the container until he receives a visual confirmation in the top of his screen that the twist locks are being safely locked. Matias lifts the spreader and boom into a suitable driving position. Then he checks the rear-view camera and the map screen to make sure that nothing is behind the vehicle, reverses and heads towards the container's target location. Once arrived, the target position is being highlighted by a bright rectangle on the ground. Matias slowly lowers the container inside the marked area and opens the twist locks to release it.

Later, Matias has selected a job for which he needs to pick a container on a truck trailer. After having picked up the container, he makes his way to a corridor between the container stacks where he is supposed to find the truck (see Figure 19). The ideal path to the loading area is visualized in front of him. As Matias arrives at the loading area, the truck's number plate is being recognized and displayed in the augmented camera view as soon as it comes in view. The system confirms that it matches the number plate of the expected target truck.

The reach stacker now approaches the trailer from the side for placing the container. Matias then uses the twist lock position visualization to accurately position the spreader on the container's corners. He lowers the spreader and makes small adjustments to its position and rotation according to the visualizations. As the spreader snaps onto the container, Matias engages the twist locks.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

The twist lock status must always be accurately and reliably communicated.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

It must not be possible to reverse while the container is not yet lifted in a safe height.

PUX concept: Immediate feedback on the verification of the correct truck, reducing mental load and avoiding that containers are loaded on the wrong target truck. Approved by four out of five operators.

Figure 20: Persons (e. g., truck driver) detected next to truck (image: VTT)

Now he needs to wait for the truck driver to open all the container locks in the four bottom corners. **During this, the truck driver is being recognized by the object detection system and his position is constantly being highlighted on the map view, on the main screen and its frame, indicating the movement and distance of the truck driver (see Figure 20).** For a while, the truck driver seems to be busy behind the trailer, with load banging of metal being heard. As he appears again, he makes hand signs that Matias does not immediately understand, but it seems like something is wrong with one of the twist locks. By pressing a button and speaking into a microphone, Matias now directly addresses the truck driver. Speaking some words in broken English, the driver confirms that one of the twist locks was stuck and he needed to get it loose with a hammer, but now all locks are open. The driver gives a thumbs up and walks back to the truck cabin. Now Matias can lift the container safely and move it into transport position, always paying attention to the position of the truck driver.

PUX concept: While being a main safety feature, the person and object detection also contributes to the feeling of safety, avoiding that personnel or other vehicles near the reach stacker could be overlooked, especially due to large dead angles, taking away cognitive load and stress. Approved by five out of five operators.

Moving a 40ft container from- and to a stack with intermediate steps

For his next job, Matias has to transport a 40ft container to another area of the port for loading onto a vessel later. **As he checks the container information on the job selection screen, the system shows that the target container is in a stack below another container of the same size, making rearrangements necessary to pick it up. To find out more about the top container in the stack, he selects it in the job information screen, where he can access information about any container on the terminal whenever needed. He sees that the container was placed there yesterday and is waiting to be moved to a truck later that day. Matias activates a filter view on the terminal map showing only free slots for 40ft containers where they don't block any other container that is associated with a job today. Luckily, he finds several spots where he can place the top container in the stack without impeding his colleagues or himself later.**

PUX concept: Efficient planning of lifts and temporary placements of containers “in the way”. Avoiding container placements that block other target containers associated with tasks later in the day could reduce the total needed number of lifts per day by around 40%, according to one operator. This feature would likely contribute greatly to efficiency and self-efficacy. Approved by five out of five operators.

Figure 21: Top-down view of spreader (image: VTT)

Figure 22: Visualization for safe reach based on container weight (image: VTT)

While approaching the container head-on, he extends the spreader to its widest configuration. Matias again uses the XR visualizations and the top-down camera view (see Figure 21) to move the spreader in a suitable position and lowers it until the twist locks engage automatically. As soon as the system indicates that the twist locks are engaged, he lifts the container. He moves the spreader and boom back into a suitable position for transport. To make the transport of the bulky container safer, he activates a function that enables an XR visualization of the container's outer corners on the ground, helping Matias to estimate the distance he needs to keep from container stacks and other vehicles in the tight corridors of the port. As he arrives at the empty spot on the ground and places the container.

Now he needs to return to the container that he needed to move for his current job. After going through the same procedure and carrying the target container to its destination on top of another stack, he lifts the container up, paying close attention to the XR visualizations that show him how far he can safely extend the heavy container without losing stability and tipping the vehicle over (see Figure 22). Normally, placing such a wide container high up on a stack would be rather challenging, but with the XR projections of the container corners and haptic feedback from the joystick when the corners perfectly align with those of the container below, he quickly finds the right alignment and can set the container down.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

The system should generally not interfere with the operator's actions, but it must not be possible to extend the boom with a container beyond the safe limit for its weight to avoid tipping over.

End of workday

As the workday ends, Matias steers the reach stacker back to the vehicle garage. Once arrived, he sends the vehicle into standby, logs out of the vehicle control interface and opens the summary of the day, which includes a timelapse recording of the vehicle's movement on the port over the course of the day, visualizing the area driven with a coloured line, and an overview of the reach stacker team's achievements of the day, e. g., the number and mass of containers moved, the estimated value of the cargo delivered today and the distance driven. Recordings of Matias' own work can only be seen by himself, while team achievements can also be seen by colleagues who were involved. Other colleagues and supervisors cannot access this information.

PUX concepts: Visualization of movement during the day and achievements of the team to convey self-efficacy and meaningfulness. It is important that supervisors cannot access this information, since that could lead to pressure on the operators resulting in negative feelings. Both concepts approved by four out of five operators each.

4.3 UC3: Construction

In preparation of the co-design phase, an ideation workshop was held in October 2023 to collect suggestions for technologies and concepts that may be of interest to excavator operators and mitigate the problems and environmental threats detailed in deliverable D3.1/D3.6 (final). After collection, the ideas were evaluated by the consortium partners in terms of technical feasibility and usefulness (output) for the operators. As is shown in **Figure 23**, the evaluation resulted most of the discussed technologies and functions to be considered feasible and useful. Only for laser projections and the idea of a “smart spotlight” which had originated in UC1 talks, no immediate applicability was found.

Figure 23: Screenshot of UC3 ideation workshop results

Summarized, this resulted in the following feature ideas that were integrated in the initial vision scenario:

- Recognition of excavation markings in the real world and automatic transfer of excavation dimensions to the digital terrain model (with options for customisation)
- Display of the type and position of lines in the work area (gas, water, electricity, telephone & internet cables)
- Laser projection of excavation pit boundaries, lines within the working area and various auxiliary lines (minimum distance from the excavation pit depending on vehicle weight, clearance between excavation pit and excavation deposit area) on the ground in front of the vehicle
- Ambient lights (light strips) around the windscreen, which indicate the distance of the bucket corners (left and right) to the target depth of the excavation pit (colour coding and distance of the light signal from the "centre line")

- Detection of objects (people, vehicles) in the vicinity of the vehicle or within the working area. Detected objects are displayed on the screen. If an object enters the working area, the vehicle operator's attention is drawn by a warning signal from the ambient lights and an acoustic signal.

These ideas were validated and expanded during co-design workshops near Glauchau, Germany, in March 2024. Most of the ideas were approved and expanded by operators with minor changes or comments. Three additional functions generated during vision scenario creation were not approved: The automatic calibration of moving parts (e. g., hydraulic cylinder compression, bucket and stick position and angle) based on LIDAR measurement (which was deemed fault-prone), the projection of laser patterns on the ground to warn nearby pedestrians, co-workers or vehicles of entering the excavator's work area (which was deemed to be useless or even distracting), and visual feedback on approximating a critical weight of soil in the bucket (which was deemed situational for specific types of jobs and excavators, but usually not a concern).

An interim version of the operator-validated vision scenarios was presented in the first version of this deliverable, D3.2. For the next phase of information scenario co-design, another co-design workshop involving excavator operators and trainers from the ÜAZ Glauchau construction training centre, Germany, were held in May 2024. In these workshops, information requirements and ideas for visualizations and data depictions in the cabin were collected and discussed. Based on this input, information architecture and design concepts for a matrix display on the stick, ambient light bars in the wind screen frame and tablet screens inside the cabin were developed. The concepts were presented to excavator operators and trainers, discussed and validated in another workshop in February 2025.

Based on conversations in the workshops in May 2024 and February 2025, concepts for positive user experience (PUX) specifically for UC3 were first ideated by the HdM-internal team and then also validated with excavator operators and trainers in a workshop in June 2025.

In **Table 6**, we present the final integrated interaction scenario for UC3, expanding the interim vision scenarios from D3.2 with descriptions of the conceptual sources and use of information. The descriptions are complemented by operator-validated wireframes and drafts in the first column, which present an idea of how the information requirements of the operators could be met by a future system. These wireframes present concepts, not polished interface designs, and should not be understood as the only possible solution. Text passages marked in blue represent operator-validated PUX concepts, which are commented in the third column. Text passages marked in yellow represent safety-critical functions or procedures that require careful handling or specific rules in terms of interaction design to avoid danger. Recommendations for the interaction design of these functions and procedures are also added in the third column.

Table 6: Validated UC3 interaction scenario

Visualization (Exemplary for selected technologies and functions, not matching the scenario descriptions in their entirety)	Scenario ■ Yellow: Safety-critical elements and procedures ■ Blue: Integrated concepts for positive user experience (PUX)	Additional comments on marked passages ■ Yellow: Design recommendations ■ Blue: Explanation of PUX concepts
<p>Figure 24: Excavators on construction site</p>	<p>Introduction</p> <p>Jonas is a young excavator operator who has recently completed his training. As he arrives at his workplace in the morning, an industrial construction site (see Figure 24), he is handed a digging permit by the foreman and instructed to start by excavating a rectangular pit in which a connection to existing cable lines in the ground is to be made the next day by another construction company. The location is already marked with spray paint on the gravel.</p> <p>Before he sets off, Jonas' foreman pats him on the back and tells him that his assigned excavator for the day is equipped with the THEIA assistance system, so he will not have to worry too much about accidents despite his limited experience and the large, busy construction site.</p>	
<p>Figure 25: Top bar of the main screen showing essential vehicle data and functions</p>	<p>Preparations and planning</p> <p>Jonas carries out a visual inspection of the vehicle, starts the excavator's engine, lets it warm up briefly and checks that all systems are working. The tablet in the excavator switches on automatically and he sees the start screen. He looks at the information displayed in the top bar, including system parameters such as the GPS signal, operating hours, fuel level, gear and driving mode (see Figure 25). In addition, he checks the temperature indicators for engine oil, hydraulic oil and coolant. Everything seems to be normal.</p>	

Figure 26: Main screen showing warnings and reports

In the pop-up in the centre of the screen he notices a hint that AdBlue will need to be refuelled in about 100 operating hours (see Figure 26). Jonas forwards this message to his company’s workshop with the press of a button and closes the hint. Below that hint he sees a list of all the routine checks that have to be completed before he can start working. He ticks off those he has already completed and works through the remaining ones. Once complete, the list disappears, and he sees a new message: “All systems ready”

He skims through the last reports from previous operators of the vehicle and reads that one colleague mentioned that the fuel consumption seemed to be a bit higher than usual. Jonas decides to pay attention to that during his shift. Since he does not have to do an infield design right now, he taps on the button “main screen”.

PUX concept: Immediate feedback on the vehicle’s operational readiness, reducing mental load and avoiding that any checks are forgotten or done more often than needed. Approved by six out of six operators.

Figure 27: Excavation pit borders projected on ground

Jonas notices that the current excavator attachment is not the right one for his job, so he switches it. The system recognized that the attachment has been changed and shows a window where Jonas selects the one he has just coupled in order to configure it.

Now that the vehicle is operational, Jonas drives the excavator towards the area the foreman has shown him.

As he approaches the marked spot on the ground, the assistance system picks up the markings. Jonas confirms that he wants to register the markings as a new excavation pit, then a bright projected laser rectangle lights up around the marked area, which Jonas can adjust on the top-down map view on the tablet on his right-hand side (see Figure 27). The length and width of the pit have already been correctly registered by the system and are displayed on the screen, so Jonas now only has to set the depth of the pit and the embankment angle.

Critical interaction design recommendation: While the ground projection feature is considered useful, it may not work in bright daylight. Laser projection must not be so strong or angled in a way that they could harm other operators or bystanders.

Figure 28: Main screen showing top-down view and a person behind the vehicle

Figure 29: Selection of secondary screen (split screen)

Configuration of main screen

Next, he configures the views on his tablet. By default, he sees the top-down map view in full-screen mode (see Figure 28). He minimizes this and can now choose either the bucket view or the side view for the top part of the screen (see Figure 29). The bucket view shows the current bucket angle and tilt as well as the target surface.

He also sees a button for a ground-penetrating radar scan which might come in handy when working close to suspected underground structures, but he doesn't need it right now.

The side view shows the bottom part of the excavator and the excavation pit from the side, including the position and type of known lines. Jonas can also see the how much space is between the bucket tip and the next line. He chooses this view.

At the bottom of the screen, he can open a menu containing visibility toggles and a legend for underground and above-ground structures. The above ground mode shows the outline of the excavation pit, the swivelling area and restricted areas. The underground mode shows the position and type of known lines. Persons and objects close to the excavator are always shown with highlighted dots on the screen. By tapping on the icons of the above ground areas and underground lines, Jonas has the option to change the colours and save them to his user settings. However, for now he leaves the default settings. Jonas activates the above ground mode, then he closes the menu.

The tablet offers three different texture views for the environment of the vehicle: A realistic textured environment with trench outline, a 3D scan and a color-coded height deviation visualization, which can be switched by swiping gestures. Jonas compares the views and chooses the default textured view. As a final step before starting with the excavation, Jonas makes sure that the bucket counter in the bottom right corner of the screen is reset to 0.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

This feature assumes that the position of structures in the ground is known and mostly accurate, which is not yet the case in every country or area. Thus, a representation of the position of underground structures must communicate uncertainty and must not lead the operator to ignore warning signs of imminent collisions with underground lines in the physical reality (e. g., sand layers, streamers in the soil).

Figure 30: Split screen with side-view showing an electrical line proximity warning

Pit excavation

Jonas decides to start with the top right-hand edge of the pit. As he digs the bucket blade into the soil, the light bars on the left and right of the front window show with a colour gradient how close the right and left corners of the bucket are to the target level. The same is also shown on the left and right edge of the tablet screen. While Jonas swivels the machine to the left, he keeps an eye on the vehicle's surroundings shown in the bottom part of the screen. While digging, he focuses on the underground lines displayed in the side view in the upper part of the screen.

Jonas sees a power line at a depth of 50cm under the excavation pit. As Jonas continues to dig, a proximity warning appears and the line starts to flash on the display. This shows Jonas that the bucket appears to be very close to it and could damage the power line (see Figure 30).

He decides to try the ground-penetrating radar scan to check how deep the line really is. By placing the bucket on the ground and pressing the GPR scan button on the tablet, a small radar attachment extends down to the ground and performs a scan. The system shows that a metallic object has been detected at a depth of around 70cm below the current bottom of the excavation pit, so Jonas learns that he can complete his excavation without the danger of damaging the power line.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

Warnings of imminent collisions with structures or bystanders must be clear and consistent in their modality.

Critical interaction design recommendation:

The GPR can only estimate the position and size of certain structures in the ground. Its feedback should be communicated as "there is something around depth Y" rather than "there is structure X in depth Y".

Figure 31: Light feedback flashing red, warning of a close object on the right vehicle side

As Jonas continues to dig and unloads the soil to the right, he suddenly hears a warning signal from the right cabin speakers and the light bars on his right-hand side flash red (see Figure 31). Alarmed, Jonas looks at the right-hand screen, which shows that one of his colleagues is carelessly walking past near the vehicle, apparently oblivious to the danger he is in due to being in the blind spot behind the excavator's boom. Jonas waits for him to pass by and then continues the excavation.

Every now and then, he checks a progress bar displayed on the screen, which visualizes the amount of soil still needed to be moved and the time he will likely need for that at the current pace based on an estimation of the mass of soil in the excavation pit's dimensions. This allows him to get a rough idea of how long this task is going to take.

Later, the foreman returns, approaches the work area from the left and also appears on the map screen. As Jonas notices him, he moves the control lever back, stopping any machine movement and inputs, and leans out of the door. He is informed that his next task is to excavate a narrow, straight trench from the finished pit to another cable access point in the ground twelve metres away.

PUX concept: While being a main safety feature, the person and object detection also contributes to the feeling of safety, avoiding that bystanders near the excavator could be overlooked, taking away cognitive load and stress. Approved by six out of six operators.

PUX concept: Keeping track of progress, conveying the feeling of self-efficacy and plannability. Approved by four out of six operators. Supervisors should not be able to access this information since that could cause additional pressure on operators and rejection of this kind of feature.

To excavate the trench, Jonas turns the excavator and aligns it in the centre and parallel to the direction of the planned trench. He opens the infield design menu and drags a rectangle into the system to define it as a new excavation pit.

	<p>He then adjusts its position and dimensions.</p> <p>At the same time, the planned trench is projected onto the ground in front of the excavator, allowing the foreman to confirm the correct position from the outside.</p> <p>As soon as the trench has reached the desired depth at Jonas' comfortable working distance, he swivels the boom 180 degrees to the left, moves the vehicle back a few metres and then swivels 180 degrees to the left again to excavate the next part of the trench.</p>	<p>Critical interaction design recommendation:</p> <p>As mentioned further above: While the ground projection feature is considered useful, it may not work in bright daylight. Laser projection must not be so strong or angled in a way that they could harm other operators or bystanders.</p>
<p>Figure 32: Report screen with option to add an own report</p>	<p>End of workday</p> <p>Jonas places the bucket on the ground and moves the boom, arm and bucket in a way that the upper hydraulic cylinders are extended as little as possible. He puts the control lever back to lock all moving parts, takes his foot off the accelerator and switches off the engine. Jonas has paid attention to the fuel consumption, but did not notice anything unusual, so he opens the reports in the upper right corner of the tablet display and marks the last report as resolved.</p> <p>Jonas also wants to leave a report himself. He usually does that on the tablet by typing or leaving a voice message which is then transcribed (see Figure 32). However, today he decides to do it on his phone. He opens his usual messenger app on his phone and navigates to an already existing chat with a number that is linked to the reports on this particular excavator. He types a brief report and adds the label “normal”, since there were no issues in the operation today. Once Jonas sends the message, it will appear on the tablet as a new report.</p> <p>Finally, Jonas sends the workday recording from the THEIA system to his phone. The recording is a fast-forward video of the vehicle’s movement and excavations taken from a front camera mounted on the cabin. He plans to show it to his parents later that day, who initially inspired him to apply for a job in construction.</p> <p>Before he can switch off the machine completely, he waits another minute until the AdBlue has been pumped out of the engine and the machine emits a high-pitched signal tone.</p>	<p>PUX concept: Video recording both for learning and self-improvement purposes and for sharing the experience with friends and family (connectedness). Approved by four out of six operators. As mentioned above, supervisors should not be able to access this information.</p>

5 Conclusions

This deliverable defines and summarizes the transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design methodology applied in THEIA^{XR} and presents the interim results generated by this approach. The active involvement of vehicle operators in the co-design activities has proven to be of great value for the project, with several highly impactful new feature ideas and information requirements having been raised and emphasized by operators in co-design workshops that may otherwise not have come to mind. Not just the identification of these features and requirements, but also the reasoning behind them and the reasoning behind the disapproval of certain ideas has been enormously insightful.

Beyond the results, feedback from operators and R&D stakeholders regarding the application of our scenario-based co-design approach has been very positive. The scenario-based design methodology allowed operators to immediately grasp, correct and expand our understanding of the status quo of vehicle operation and our ideas on how to improve it with XR technologies in the future. The flexible but concrete scenarios incorporating technical terms and typical situations known to the operators and the on-site workshops in their known environments facilitated vivid discussions, often continuing even after the official end of the workshops and in one case even leading to an excavator operator demonstrating an additional safety issue to the co-design moderator directly on one of the machines nearby.

Finally, looking back at the entire scenario-based co-design process from 2023 to 2025, there are two more major learnings we want to point out for any future projects with the intention to employ co-design methods specifically in technical fields, such as but not limited to the off-highway domain:

- **Regular involvement of end-users has proven to be far more challenging than expected, despite partners in the consortium with direct access to operators or customer contacts having been informed about the issue in the very beginning of the project.** The challenge can be broken down into three main issues. First, operators and stakeholders in our project (UC1 and UC3) preferred and vehemently insisted on on-site workshops instead of online workshops. This may be associated with the practical nature of their work or an already existing perceived overload of online meetings. On-site meetings proved to be beneficial for discussions and results but also demanded much higher time and traveling budget. Second, companies outside of the consortium that employ end-users have barely reacted to requests for participation at all, despite shared interests and the promise of incentives. Third, the co-design partners that we did manage to acquire all had domain-specific limitations to their availability, which meant that the schedule of co-design workshops had to be constantly adjusted and shifted.
- **Co-design activities would be most useful far ahead of the start of technical development to allow the prioritization of feasible and accepted technologies and functions before any effort is spent on the ones that operators do not approve of.** Over the course of the project, some function concepts were dropped that initially seemed like good ideas but were either rejected by operators or turned out to have low applicability. If conceptual co-design phases such as problem and vision scenario development – assuming that participant recruitment and involvement goes according to plan – could have started a year before the beginning of technical development, this “wasted effort” (even though it may have resulted in interesting explorations of technology) could have been entirely avoided. This applies even more for the intended use of transdisciplinary co-design in actual product development processes in the industry, where any changes to requirements later than in the initial phase could mean major disruptions and even the cancellation of a project. For Horizon Europe RIA projects intended to employ co-design in combination with technical development, it would thus be recommended to allow and ask for flexible work plans where specific co-design work packages start ahead of technical work packages.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

[XR]	Extended Reality
[UC]	Use Case
[ELSA]	Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects
[HCD]	Human-Centred Design
[HMD]	Head-Mounted Display
[TAM]	Technology Acceptance Model
[6DoF]	Six Degrees of Freedom
[R&D]	Research & Development
[HMI]	Human-Machine Interface
[RC]	Remote Control